

ABOUT FINE-GRAINED CONCRETE

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Annotation: This paper investigates the strength properties of the fine-grained concrete reinforced with the amorphous fiber based on the Fe-B-C system and obtained by the "spinning" method, and concretes reinforced with commercially available types of fibers: fiber based on mineral wool, basalt fiber, fiberglass, steel and polypropylene fibers.

Keywords: fiber, fine-grained concrete, amorphous fiber, strength properties, fiber reinforced materials, fiber-reinforced concrete cements, binders concretes, cementitious concrete, mechanical activation

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the actual direction of the development of high-quality cement concretes, characterized by a wider range of functional capabilities, is the use of complex additives that combine components with various functional purposes. Such additives allow to effectively manage the processes of structure formation at all stages of the technology of concrete preparation and, as a result, allow to obtain the concrete with various high-performance properties [1–3].

To increase the strength characteristics of modern concrete, various technical and technological solutions are used, including dispersed reinforcement with fibers. This type of building material is called fiber- reinforced concrete. The industry of modern building materials demonstrates various types of fibers used in the manufacture of the fiber-reinforced concrete. Fibers of both artificial and natural origin are used.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the article [7] the authors use waste in the production of mineral wool as an additive to concrete. The compressive strength of the obtained materials reaches 80 MPa. Moreover, these specimens are characterized by high water resistance.

Also, some fibers of organic origin are used for the dispersed reinforcement. The jute fibers have a positive effect on the flexural and compressive strengths [1]. The authors of articles [3] consider sisal fiber as dispersed reinforcement. The results demonstrate that the sisal fiber reinforcement could provide the same level of residual strength for concrete as the polypropylene fiber reinforcement.

The main issue of optimizing the geometric parameters and the physical properties of the fiber is the need to ensure reliable adhesion of the fiber to the cement matrix under loads, as well as resistance to withstand tensile forces [2]. The interfacial connection of the fiber and the matrix is very important – it helps to counteract the shear stress transmitted from the cement matrix to the fibers at the interface. As the adhesion increases, the resulting cement composites become more durable and elastic due to the transmission of the arising tangential stresses from the concrete to the fibers. The results of experimental studies of the influence of the type, length, and amount of reinforcing fibers on the structure and strength of the fiber-reinforced concrete are presented in [3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1. Polypropylene fiber.

Figure 2. Basalt fiber.

Figure 3. Fiberglass.

Figure 4. Mineral wool fiber.

The field of application of the fine-grained concrete and its characteristics depend on the properties of the fiber material. Currently three main types of dispersed micro-reinforcement are used abroad: fibers as short cuts of steel thin wire, glass and polypropylene fibers. Authors of this paper suggest using six different types of dispersed

reinforcement: polypropylene, basalt, glass-fiber, mineral wool, steel and amorphous (Table 1).

Table 1. Technical characteristics of different fibers.

Indicator	Polypropylene fiber	Basalt fiber	Fiber-glass fiber	Mineral wool fiber	Steel fiber	Amorphous fiber
Material	Polypropylene	Basalt fiber	Glass fiber	Mineral wool	Carbon steel wire	Fe-B-C alloy
Fiber diameter	10–25 μm	13–17 μm	13–15 μm	15–30 μm	0,5–1,2 mm	30 μm
Fiber length	6–18 mm	3.2–15.7 mm	4.5–18 mm	0.5–1 mm	30–50 mm	35 mm
Melting temperature $^{\circ}\text{C}$	160	1450	860	1110	1550	1700
Corrosion resistance	Low	High	Medium	High	Medium	Medium

To obtain the amorphous fiber the multicomponent amorphous metal alloy (metallic glass) was used. This alloy of the Fe-B-C system consisting of Mo (up to 20 %), Cr (up to 17 %), and V (6 %) was obtained at the “Material Science and Technology” department of «Institute of Metallurgy, Mechanical Engineering and Transport» of Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University.

The initial ingots (40–50 g) of multicomponent alloys were made in quartz crucibles using high frequency currents (HFC). Melting was carried out in stages. At the first stage, the components of the Fe-B-C alloy in a certain weight ratio were melted in vacuum. Secondly the crucible was filled with an inert gas, after which sparingly soluble alloying additives were introduced into the melt in the order of their reaction activity (Cr, Mo, V). Overheating at 200–500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ above the melting temperature ensured complete dissolution of the components and a fairly uniform alloy structure.

In the following stage after melting, the necessary gas pressure in the crucible (Δp) is created and the melt is squeezed out in the form of a thin (fraction of a millimeter) jet onto a drum rotating at a speed of Vd . The drum is made of copper and rotates at a speed

that provides a linear surface speed, and, consequently, provides a linear speed of the tape up to 50 m/s. The jet of melt drops at a speed V_m at an angle α to the surface, as a result, a stationary pool of melt is formed on the surface of the refrigerator drum [7].

CONCLUSION

At this stage of the studies of the amorphous fiber of the Fe-B-C system and the comparison of its effect on the mechanical-and-physical properties of the fine-grained concrete with other types of fibers, the following conclusions may be highlighted:

1. The addition of the amorphous fibers in various concentrations to the cement composite leads to an increase of 56 % in the flexural strength, but decreases the compressive strength by 30 % compared to the control specimens.

2. The steel fiber showed an increase of 20 % in flexural strength and an increase of 14 % in compressive strength, which confirms the positive effect of adding a commercially available fiber to the fine- grained concrete.

3. The selected percentages (1, 2, 3 % of the weight of the control concrete grout) for all the above- mentioned fibers, except the polypropylene fiber, are optimal because of absence of the "hedgehogs" (fiber clumping).

4. The compressive strength decreases for all the observed fiber-reinforced concrete specimens (except the specimens with the steel fiber) compared to the control specimens. This fact proves that fibers, like dispersed inclusions in a concrete, adversely affect the compressive strength.

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